

Psycho – Spiritual Adaptability of Mama Day in Gloria Naylor’s *Mama Day*

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Abstract

“Psycho Spirituality” becomes a natural medication through which the soul or the ‘True Self’ attains the spiritual truth. In *Mama Day*, Gloria Naylor uses her ancient inheritance of magic and herbal medicine, the weapons of women, sinking all the rational thoughts underneath the suffrage status, unfolding the potential of women. *Mama Day*, a timeless generational saga, a tale of the supernatural power and homage to the redemptive power of African American traditions that span into two worlds; the southern barrier in island of Willow Springs, a place exempted not only from the laws of nature but from the racial laws of men; the other world, New York City, the polyglot, multi-racial, governed by strict and seemingly heartless codes of love. She digs and probes required reconciliations between the blacks’ rural past and their urban present; between myth and history, between individuals and communities, and faith and logic. *Mama Day* would communicate with nature which is reflected in her vision of using supernatural powers. *Mama Day* brings up the validity of her meditative healing with the mystical state to get rid of depression and anxiety to maintain the transpersonal relationship and their integrity. There arises a new evolution of consciousness which makes them forget their previous identification to lead to her identity of “self.”

Keywords: psycho-spirituality, magic, herbal medicine, healing, transpersonal.

Psycho-Spiritual adaptability is a concept which pertains to the relationship between spirituality and the mind wherein the soul becomes the catalyst to preserve the values of life, spiritualizing of psychology, interpreting or explaining through our deeds and relationship despite the so-called Imperialism, black female oppression, East-West conflicts, and racism. To have a real escape from the world of alienation, or to transcend the spirit from the alleviation, “Psycho Spirituality” becomes a natural medication through which the soul or the ‘True Self’ attains the spiritual truth. It gives oneness to our heart, soul and body, which help move further in any activity beyond our knowledge. Naturally, the mind is free to think of some positive progression leaving the problems and receiving a new transformation to solve the previous issues, by concentrating

on other developmental resources. The humanistic philosopher and psychoanalyst Erich Fromm expresses that the psychoanalytic patients suffered from an “inner deadness” and an “alienation from oneself.” Fromm continues that:

Zen is the art of seeing into the nature of one's being; it is a way from bondage to freedom; it liberates our natural energies; ... and it impels us to express our faculty for happiness and love [...] [W]hat can be said with more certainty is that the knowledge of Zen, and a concern with it, can have a most fertile and clarifying influence on the theory and technique of psychoanalysis. Zen, different as it is in its method from psychoanalysis, can sharpen the focus, throw new light on the nature of insight, and heighten the sense of what it is to see, what it is to be creative, what it is to overcome the affective contaminations and false intellectualizations which are the necessary results of experience based on the subject-object split (140).

Naylor's character Mama Day finds “a way from bondage to freedom” which “liberates” her “natural energies” to lead her people to possess “happiness and love.” Naylor makes her women characters undergo all these struggles but to give a spiritual encounter to strengthen their adaptability with a resilient nature or a transformation to enhance their development from the darker phase to the brighter side of consciousness during trials and tribulations. The Psycho-spiritual approach is highly subjective and very personal and close to heart. Naylor provides the characters with the correct directions to get along with their lives.

Each novel has the uniqueness of presenting the characters, especially women, to maintain a well-balanced relationship to renewing their community living to give moral support to African American people. All the five novels *The Women of Brewster Place* (1982), *Linden Hills* (1985), *Mama Day* (1988), *Bailey's Café* (1992), and *The Men of Brewster Place* (1999). The Women of Brewster Place has seven women whose survival techniques made them happy despite their odds of life or threatened external forces with their strong binding of relationship maintained as their diversified black female experiences. They escape from their ghettos mentally resisting physical, mental, and spiritual violence with their bondage of friendship.

In *Mama Day*, Naylor uses her ancient inheritance of magic and herbal medicine, the weapons of women, sinking all the rational thoughts underneath the suffrage status, unfolding the potential of women. African American women were required “to fill the role of angel of some one else's house, cooking, cleaning, washing, sewing, nursing, and rising or even bearing the children of the master/employer” (Hayes 669). Naylor creates a strong foundation for the new hope of community living by setting aside all social bureaucracies. *Mama Day*, a timeless generational saga, a tale of the supernatural power and homage to the redemptive power of African American traditions that span into two worlds; the southern barrier in island of Willow Springs, a place exempted not only from the laws of nature but from the racial laws of men; the other world, New York City, the polyglot, multi-racial, governed by strict and seemingly heartless codes of love. She digs and probes required reconciliations between the blacks' rural past and their urban present; between myth and history, between individuals and communities, and faith and logic. Symbolically, she reconciles the scattered children of Africa with their first, home.

Mama Day recounts the lives of Miranda. “Miranda functions as a healer and visionary, whose abilities to save children's lives, birth babies, and provide aid and succour to the ill are legendary on the island” and, Mama Day's “powers of conjure-used-for-good bring peace to the island and its environs (Duran 4).” Her healing works as therapy on all the three levels: physical, mental and spiritual wherein the psychological and spiritual experience get matured to create a psychospiritual perspective and transpersonal surface with individuality and freedom of mind and thought. It is a kind of psycho-therapy to clear the clutter from the mind and body.

Naylor employs three alternating voices in the introductory pages. The first voice belongs to the omniscient Mama Day and her sister Abigail; the second voice belongs to Abigail's granddaughter, Ophelia also called Cocoa because of her light brown skin, living in New York City and coming back to Willow Springs on the occasion of Candle Walk.

Willow Springs. Everybody knows but nobody talks about the legend of Sapphira Wade. Sapphire Wade. A true conjure woman: satin black, biscuit cream, red as Georgia clay; depending on which of us takes a mind to her. She could walk through a lightning storm without being touched; grab a bolt of lightning in the palm of her hand; use the heat of lightning to start the kindling going under her medicine pot: depending on which of us takes a mind to her. (Naylor 3)

Nostalgia is a way to go back to their past and relive their lost identity. Naylor brings back her identity when she "implicitly juxtaposes active and passive forms of nostalgia through her depiction of Cocoa's and Georgia's reflections on Willow Springs, a home space that exists in memory, in imagination, and in its material reality" (Lamothe 156).

The conjure woman is called as "Sappira Wade" (Hayes 674), the representative of the land. Sapphira's death is immortalised in a local ritual called Candle Walk which takes the place of Christmas, itself tainted by commercialism when the residents of Willow Springs provide extra food and supplies to families whose crop did not do well that year. They march throughout the town carrying candles, singing and chanting "Lead on with light, Great Mother" (Naylor 111). Harmony between Willow Springs' communities is restored at Candle Walk:

Things took a little different turn with the young folks having more money and working beyond the bridge. They started buying each other fancy gadgets from the catalogues, and you'd hear ignorant things like, 'They ain't gave me nothing last Candle Walk, so they getting the same from me this year.... There's a disagreement every winter about whether these young people spell the death of Candle Walk'. (Naylor 111)

Miranda's magic of striking Ruby's house with lightning makes everyone sick. George is helpless. Cocoa undergoes hallucination. Miranda knows very well that she needs George's help to rescue Cocoa. Miranda could command natural forces and could feel on-coming natural disasters. Her supernatural powers do not derive only from a mythical past but her experience of Willow Springs. Mama Day would communicate with nature which is reflected in her vision of using supernatural powers. "A wave over a patch of zinnias and the scarlet petals take flight . . . Winged marigolds follow them into the air. A thump of the stick: morning glories start to sing" (152). Miranda could interpret the signs and sounds of Willow Springs a real gift of African-derived tradition of divination: "these generally double-sided characters act as mediators between this world and the other, between men and gods, and between the rational and the intuitive" (143). "Outside white traditions, Willow Springs – with its Candle Walk instead of Christmas, its "standingforth" in lieu of funerals – is culturally independent as well" (Meisenhelder 405).

Mama Day also practices such grounds, in which George and Cocoa meet each other. Prospero, through his magic power, controls each and every things as well as people and, on the other hand; Mama Day, through her supernatural powers, controls and protects the Willow Springs and its folks. As Prospero uses his magic to control Caliban with the crudest sorts of physical punishment and eventually liberates Ariel, as Mama Day uses her powers to control hurricane, Bernice and witch Ruby and sets free Junior Lee from Ruby's trap. Thus, control is central to the use of magic—control of creatures, spirits, natural elements and finally other human beings. Master of the isle and its residents as he was once King of Naples, Prospero uses sorcery as quasi—legitimate extension of his rule. Miranda has tremendous power but she does not practice magic. She mostly uses her herbs as well as seeds and relies upon the prescribed waiting period.

Mama Day shows a nonstop progression in her artistic imagination. Gloria Naylor creates the perfect conjure woman in Mama Day. She is much closer to her roots than the rest of Willow Springs, as is demonstrated with her conversations with her dead father and her experience while making the wedding quilt. She inherits her mantle of power from her great grandmother who the reader knows is versed in midwifery and witchcraft from the prefatory documents of the novel. Mama Day follows in her footsteps as a midwife and herbal doctor to her people. (Selvaraj 285)

Mama Day brings up the validity of her meditative healing with the mystical state to get rid of depression and anxiety to maintain the transpersonal relationship and their integrity. There arises a new evolution of consciousness which makes them forget their previous identification to lead to her identity of the “self.” Storhoff feels that “Naylor achieves in *Mama Day* what Gates calls a “speakerly text” – one that “would seem primarily to be oriented toward imitating one of the numerous forms of oral narration to be found in classical Afro-American vernacular literature” and “Mama Day’s voice serves as a spiritual ballast in the narrative, a guide to elemental truths (Storhoff 35).

When our body, mind, and soul work together, our psychotherapy leads to holistic approaches to the person with extraordinary experiences of embodiment and transpersonal experiences. Psycho-spiritual energy make a woman a holistic person to attain what is correct and what is required. Mama Day is such a woman with psycho-spiritual power to maintain smooth relations with authority. He becomes a healer and protector of her people and tradition.

Works Cited

1. Fromm, Erich, D.T. Suzuki and Richard De Martino. *Zen Buddhism and Psychoanalysis*. New York, Harper and Row, 1960. Print.
2. Hayes, Elizabeth T. “The Named and the Nameless: Morrison’s 124 and Naylor’s “the Other Place as Semiotic Choraes.”. *African American Review* Volume 38, Number 4. Winter, 2004. PP. 669-681.
3. Lamothe, Daphne. “Gloria Naylor’s Mama Day: Bridging Roots and Routes.” *African American Review*. Volume 39, Number 1/2, Spring – Summer, 2005. PP.155-169.
4. Naylor, Gloria. *Mama Day*. Vintage: 1993. Print.
5. Selvaraj, P.K. and Dr.V.N.Manjula. “Exploring the Spirituality–Texts and contexts in Gloria Naylor’s Mama Day.” *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*. Volume 6, Issue 12, December-2015. Print.
6. Storhoff, Gary. “The only voice is your own’: Gloria Naylor’s revision of *The Tempest*”. *African American Review*. Volume 29, Issue-1 1995. PP. 35-45.
7. Storhoff, Gary. “The whole Picture in Gloria Naylor’s Mama Day: Meisenhelder”, *Susan*. Volume 27, Issue 3. Autumn 1993. PP. 405-419.